

Hand Teleoperation with an Exoskeleton Enhanced by Cutaneous Haptic Feedback

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Abstract—In this work we investigate how sensory feedback in teleoperation of robotic hands can be enhanced by the addition of cutaneous haptic feedback to the conventional kineasthetic force feedback. Actuated gloves and hand exoskeletons convey kineasthetic force feedback at fingertips by grounding forces to the hand dorsum. These devices usually rely on compact actuators with a transmission and reduction stage in order to output the relatively high output forces required for rendering the contact forces and grasping strength. Such configuration however severely limits the bandwidth of the haptic device, whereas fingerpad are rich of mechano-receptors sensitive to high frequency stimuli and fast transients. In this work we aim to develop and investigate a hand exoskeleton device capable of delivering at the same time both kineasthetic force feedback and wide bandwidth cutaneous feedback. The designed device integrates high-output force linear motors, actuating the main exoskeleton kinematics, plus compact and wearable wide-bandwidth actuators mounted in series to the last link of the exoskeleton, in contact with the fingerpads. The proposed device has been developed in a prototype and experimented in preliminary grasping experiments.

Index Terms—haptic cutaneous feedback teleoperation hand exoskeleton force rendering

I. INTRODUCTION

Providing informative sensory feedback in Teleoperation of hands is a challenging task, due to the richness of haptic cues the human sensory system is able to perceive during real manipulation and haptic exploration. In conventional robotic teleoperation, force feedback provided at the end effector is usually the only haptic channel the operator is provided with. In teleoperation of hands or in virtual haptic rendering, exoskeletons or actuated gloves can be used to provide force feedback related to finger closing. However, the high number of degrees of freedom and the compact structure of a hand exoskeleton impose a trade-off in the actuation system between maximum force and high dynamics of the feedback the exoskeleton can apply to fingers [1]. In fact, the bandwidth of the system is often limited by the use of gear reduction, tendon transmissions or pneumatic actuators.

Unfortunately, in agreement with the richness of mechanoreceptors found in fingerpads [2], high frequencies cues and fast transients are very informative signals in haptic perception and especially in fine manipulation [3], [4].

Fig. 1. The experimental setup, composed of hand exoskeleton integrating additional cutaneous force feedback actuators. The teleoperated robotic hand mounts force sensors at the fingertips.

Several fingertips haptic devices have been proposed for rendering similar cutaneous cues and, some of those, feature high-dynamics actuators [5] for rendering high frequency cues (such as textures and surface features). Although wearable haptics can be used alone in a teleoperation setup, as shown in [6] where voice coil actuators have been proposed for providing wide bandwidth cutaneous haptic feedback to a surgical teleoperation system, wearable haptics alone do not provide kineasthetic force feedback related to finger opening and closing .

Based on these motivations, we propose a novel hand exoskeleton integrating both kineasthetic force feedback at finger phalanges and wide-bandwidth cutaneous force feedback provided at the fingerpad by means dedicated wearable haptic

devices. The proposed haptic system allows to enhance the user capability of perceiving the force interaction between the controlled robotic hand and the environment in a teleoperation setup.

II. THE HAND EXOSKELETON WITH ENHANCED CUTANEOUS FEEDBACK

A hand exoskeleton, presented in [7] and [8] has been used for providing kinaesthetic force feedback related to finger closing and opening. Due to the numerous DoFs of the human hand, the device has been designed adopting the under-actuation concept, focusing on grasping operations with independent fingers. Importantly, wearability issues were taken into account and addressed by a peculiar design solution with parallel, underactuated kinematics, that includes the user's finger in closure of the parallel kinematic design. Concerning the actuation of the device, linear screw actuators with DC motors have been implemented as a compact and lightweight solution with high maximum output force. Miniaturized strain gauge force sensors have been implemented to provide transparency of the device through a force-to-velocity control loop. Additional fingertip modules (Figure 1) have been added to provide wide-bandwidth cutaneous force feedback at fingerpads. Modules are based on design of wearable fingertip haptic devices presented in [9], they are actuated by linear voice coil actuators and featuring bandwidth from 0 to 250 Hz

Fig. 2. Teleoperation scheme involving two different force feedback rendering to the user: kinaesthetic and cutaneous at fingerpads.

III. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

The developed hand exoskeleton, integrated with voice-coil actuators for cutaneous feedback at fingerpads, has been preliminary experimented in simple teleoperated pinching tasks. A robotic hand implementing one independent DoF for each finger has been used in the experiment (Figure 1, right). The hand features DC electromagnetic motors with gear reduction and tendon transmission in order to actuate each finger mechanism. A miniaturized force sensor based on a deformable silicon hemisphere (Optoforce 10N) with diameter 10 mm, resolution 1 mN has been mounted at the index fingertip of the robotic hand, in direct contact with the grasped object. The general scheme of the integrated teleoperation system is shown in Figure 2. The teleoperation method implemented between

the robotic hand and the exoskeleton is a basic position-force approach. In parallel to this, measured force at the robotic fingertips have been used to drive cutaneous force feedback at fingerpads. In the experiment, the contact transient during finger closing onto a semi-rigid object (a plastic glass) has been evaluated. Results are shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Results of the manipulation experiments for the index finger.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Hand exoskeleton forces shown in Figure 3 represent an indirect measurement of forces provided to the operator as kinaesthetic force feedback related to finger closing. It is noticeable the slow dynamic of such kinaesthetic feedback due to the high-ratio gear reduction of the actuators. Conversely, filtered signals of the fingertip force sensors, filtered in order to enhance high frequencies, show a faster transient between the no contact to contact condition. Also, vibrations during increasing of the grasping strength, visible in the graph, can be informative for the operator. It is worth to note that cutaneous haptic feedback, due to the grounding of the actuators to the finger dorsum, do not interfere with stability of the system and constitute a viable option to enhance operator's perception in limited bandwidth teleoperation systems.

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